

EARTH SCIENCES

LIGNITE EXTRACTION PLANNING IN THE SIBOVČ FIELD, KOSOVO

**Hyseni A.
Panov Z.**

*Faculty of Natural and Technical Sciences,
Goce Delcev University, Stip, North Macedonia
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Abstract

The Sibovč Field represents one of the most important lignite deposits in Kosovo, serving as a strategic source for the country's electricity supply. With total reserves of approximately 990 million tones and favorable geological characteristics, it offers significant potential for long-term exploitation. This paper addresses the technical and economic planning of lignite extraction in this field, including geological analysis, selection of the extraction system, and spatial-temporal modeling. The methodology is based on a mining calendar plan, divided into key phases that encompass extraction sequencing, strategy for maximizing useful component recovery, and optimization of production rates within technical and economic constraints. Cost analysis, including depreciation and operational expenses, is essential for determining economic boundaries and optimizing the sequencing of mining zones. The results show that full consideration of capital and operational costs ensures sustainable planning and economically efficient exploitation, maximizing return on investment and ensuring the sustainable development of the mining sector in Kosovo.

Keywords: extraction planning, lignite, Sibovč Field, Kosovo

Introduction

The Sibovč Field represents one of the most important lignite deposits in Kosovo and serves as a strategic source for the country's electricity supply. It is located in the northern part of the Kosovo field area and

forms part of the Kosovo coal basin (Figure 1), together with the Bardh and Mirash deposits (Figure 2). The deposit is characterized by considerable quantities of lignite with qualities suitable for combustion in thermal power plants [1].

Figure 1. The Kosovo Coal Basin

The proven lignite reserves in this field are substantial and provide a stable basis for long-term exploitation.

According to geological and operational data, factors such as lignite seam thickness, the overburden-to-mineral ratio, and geotechnical conditions are key to

optimal extraction planning. Additionally, the open terrain and favorable climatic conditions support the use of surface mining methods.

This paper addresses the technical and economic aspects of lignite extraction planning in the Sibovc Field, including the analysis of geological conditions, selection of the mining system, and spatial-temporal modeling of operations. The aim is to provide an integrated approach for the rational management of the resource and the sustainable development of the mining sector. This paper addresses the technical and economic aspects of lignite extraction planning in the Sibovc Field, including the analysis of geological conditions, selection of the mining system, and spatial-temporal modeling of operations. The aim is to provide an integrated approach for the rational management of the resource and the sustainable development of the mining sector.

The New Sibovc Deposit is situated at an average elevation of approximately 620 meters above sea level, ranging between 500 m and 750 m. The lignite seam dips at an angle varying from 10° to 40°, with a general dip direction from southeast to southwest. The floor of the coal seam is composed of non-stratified clays with a high sand content and sandy-clayey materials, particularly in the deeper sections near the coal layer. The immediate floor consists of green clays, with the presence of plastic clays and sands. The clay layer thickness is approximately 50 meters.

The surface mine or deposit, referred to as the "Sibovc Field" (Figure 3), belongs to the Kosovo lignite basin, which corresponds to the Kosovo Plain. This basin has a longitudinal north-south orientation with an uplift trend toward the west, while its general alignment extends from the northwest to the southeast.

Figure 2. Map of potential and exploited fields in the Kosovo Lignite Basin

The Sibovc deposit is located on the western side of the Tertiary Kosovo Basin. Currently, this deposit is undergoing geological exploration and evaluation for the development of a new surface mine for lignite extraction [2,3].

The Sibovc Mine represents the largest lignite deposit in Kosovo, with total reserves estimated at 990

million tones (Mt), of which approximately 830 Mt are considered economically recoverable. The deposit covers an area of 19.7 km² (Figure 3). The overburden thickness reaches up to 50 meters, while the lignite seam exceeds 55 meters in thickness. The overburden-to-coal ratio is highly favorable, at 0.9:1 [4–7].

Figure 3. General view of Sibovci Field

Materials and Methods

The production planning for the Sibovc surface lignite mine was developed based on the construction of a calendar-based mining operations plan, which includes three fundamental phases:

Extraction sequencing, which determines the spatial and temporal order of mining operations;

Useful component recovery strategy, optimized according to production objectives;

Optimal combination of production rates, taking into account technical and economic constraints. In the initial planning phase, the ultimate pit limit and the extraction sequence are determined based on two main groups of parameters.

Geological characteristics of the deposit, including the stripping ratio, the percentage of the useful component, and the geometric location of the mineral body, Economic parameters, such as initial capital costs and operational maintenance costs.

Operating costs are essential for defining the cut-off grade and the stripping ratio [8,9]. However, the optimal approach should aim to evaluate the entire investment cycle, not just the short-term profitability of the final phases. The planning process is based on exploration data and 3D modeling of the deposit, assuming an optimal mining system, appropriate equipment sizing, and the corresponding processing operations.

The design of mining phases can be carried out manually or through computer-based methods. In the case of long-term investments, 3D deposit models are used to define the economic limits of each phase, ensuring that every phase generates a positive net value (equal profit principle). During this process, manual adjustments are required to balance the spatial distances between phases and to plan for a controlled transition into subsequent phases (Figure 4).

For financial and technical evaluation, the costs of the calendar-based mining plan are categorized into three main groups:

- Cost per ton of material extracted, which includes drilling, blasting, loading, transportation, maintenance, and administrative costs of the mine.

- Cost per ton of processed mineral, which relates to the beneficiation and treatment phases of lignite.
- Cost per unit of finished product, such as €/ton of lignite ready for market.

The capital costs for mobile equipment (bulldozers, excavators, conveyors, etc.) are amortized proportionally to the volume of material moved. Components requiring periodic replacement are included in maintenance costs and are more closely related to the volume of mineral processed [9]. Depreciation costs per ton of material typically range from €0.15 to €0.25/t, depending on equipment size, lifespan, usage intensity, and transport distances.

Inclusion of depreciation is a critical component in the economic assessment of the project, as it helps avoid underestimating the actual cost per ton. The absence of this component leads to distortion in economic optimization, favoring zones with high stripping ratios and risking the financial stability of subsequent phases.

This methodology is particularly important in deposits where the overburden-to-mineral ratio varies significantly. If mining phases focus solely on zones with immediate profit, deeper phases or those with thicker overburden risk becoming economically unfeasible [9].

To illustrate the impact of depreciation and operating costs on economic analysis, two surface mines were compared: one in the Philippines and the other in Alaska (Table 1).

This comparison revealed that differences in the stripping ratio, total costs, and depreciation strategy directly affect the net value generated by each phase and, consequently, the overall profitability of the mining project.

Figure 4. Internal phases of the pit: typical cross-section of the open-pit mine

To deepen the understanding of the impact of economic factors on lignite extraction planning, a comparative analysis was conducted between two surface mines: Mine A (Philippines) and Mine B (Alaska). The

key data for each mine are presented in Table 1. This comparison aids in identifying the dominant economic factors and in formulating effective cost management practices.

Parameter	Mine A (Philippines)	Mine B (Alaska)
Stripping Ratio (overburden/mineral)	3.2:1	5.5:1
Daily Production (t lignite)	18,000 t	14,000 t
Operating Cost per Ton of Material	0.75 €/t	1.10 €/t
Depreciation per Ton of Material	0.20 €/t	0.25 €/t
Total Cost per Ton of Material	0.95 €/t	1.35 €/t
Average Selling Price of Lignite	18.00 €/t	22.00 €/t
Cost per Ton of Lignite (including processing)	9.50 €/t	12.70 €/t
Net Value per Ton of Lignite	8.50 €/t	9.30 €/t
Net Value per Phase (Daily)	153,000 €	130,200 €

According to the data (Table 1), Mine A (Philippines) demonstrates greater efficiency in terms of pro-

duction and operational costs, offering a broad economic advantage. Mine B (Alaska) commands a higher selling price and achieves higher profit per ton, but it

also incurs higher costs and faces a less favorable stripping ratio. This analysis supports decision-making for investments, strategic planning, and resource optimization in similar mining projects, such as the case of the Sibovc deposit discussed in this study.

Results and Discussion

The analysis of lignite extraction planning in the Sibovc mining field demonstrates that the economic success of exploitation is closely linked to the accurate assessment of operating costs, depreciation, and net revenues at each mining phase. Two key parameters for determining profitability are the net value and the stripping ratio (overburden-to-mineral ratio, 0.9:1). Each exploitation phase must generate a positive net value that covers not only direct operating expenses but also capital expenditures related to the purchase, maintenance, and replacement of technical equipment. If depreciation is not included in the economic analyses, there is a risk that planned phases will focus only on zones with a high stripping ratio. This leads to the perception of high short-term profits but actually threatens the long-term economic sustainability of the project.

In the early stages of project design, many economic parameters are unknown or estimated with uncertainty. However, based on practical experience and

relevant literature, reliable estimates can be made for the following elements:

- Cost per ton of material extracted,
- - Depreciation per ton of material,
- - Cost for processing and beneficiation of lignite,
- - Administrative expenses per unit,
- - Expected mineral recovery,
- - Taxes and fees per product,
- Average market price,
- Minimum required profit per unit sold.

By integrating these parameters into the economic model, it becomes possible to:

- Determine the profitable cut-off grade,
- Define the economic limits of the pit,
- Calculate the extractable reserves, and
- Implement optimization of mining phases to maximize return on investment (Figure 5).

The results underscore the importance of an integrated approach to mine design and management, where every technical decision is grounded in thorough economic and geological analysis. Only through this balance can sustainable and economically justified exploitation of lignite in the Sibovc field be achieved.

Figure 5. Comparison between costs (extraction, processing, and production) and net value across mining phases, based on the case of the Sibovc surface lignite mine.

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